

VOCATIONAL ORIENTATION OF STUDENTS AS AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the importance of vocational guidance, taking into account their personality, the importance of vocational guidance, it is an integral part of the school educational process, the ability of students to independently and consciously choose the field of education and work goes.

Vocational guidance (vocational guidance, choice of profession, orientation to a profession, professional self-determination) is the process of identifying a person's inclinations to a certain type of professional activity. Career guidance is an acquaintance with the world of professions, the purpose of which is to choose one of them. And the more information about the specialties you have, the easier it is to analyze it and find the right one. And this is a very important step. Mistakes can be costly—literally, because higher education isn't always free, and figuratively, because it's not easy to relearn at an older age. Therefore, career guidance work at school is one of the key issues of the educational process.

One of the important goals of the education policy pursued in our country is to educate the younger generation as well-rounded people. Of course, a well-rounded person is a person who is spiritually mature, who

cares about the history, present and future of his country, as well as a person who is passionate about contributing to the economic development of society. But if an analytical approach is taken to this concept, it is possible to understand how diverse, complex and comprehensive it is in line with universal values.

It can be said that the formation of a harmoniously developed person, his acquisition of a worthy profession, the existence of a valuable force for the development of society, and thus the expression of identity in society, that is, the development of the individual. Striving for perfection is a complex process that goes hand in hand with the professional formation of an individual and lasts almost a lifetime. In the broadest sense, professional formation means that a person is educated in any profession according to his mental abilities, physical abilities, abilities, interests and aspirations, as well as

values and worldviews, and then enters and adapts to this field and finally matures over the years. and become a qualified professional. Indeed, it is an infinitely complex, irreversible, important process, and the organization of its effective use in the interests of the people is one of the most pressing problems of today.

The first and at the same time the most important stage of the process of professional formation involves the selection of a future profession, that is, the period before reaching a definite professional decision.

Career-oriented assistance allows students to take into account their personal characteristics, to be necessary for society on the one hand, to achieve their personal goals on the other hand, to independently and consciously choose the field of education and work during changing living conditions. Vocational orientation as an integral part of the educational process involves the development of their interests, abilities, skills and individual characteristics through acquaintance with the general sciences and labor activities, and takes into account the needs of society.

Innovative approach to vocational training, which is an integral part of the educational process at school, the widespread introduction of modern science-based pedagogical, psychological, information technology to improve its effectiveness, improve scientific methodological and human resources, public and parental involvement in the process. there is a need for active involvement. Because the first example in the family of a child in the acquisition of this or that profession is a teacher, a parent. Of course, a child who chooses a parenting profession will have a wide range of

opportunities. Because parents try to give their children all the love, rich experience, the secrets of their chosen profession in teaching the profession.

It should be noted that each person loves his chosen profession only if he chooses his profession independently. No matter how hard his toil is, he never gets tired and never complains. There are also parents in life who force their children to take up a profession that suits them, regardless of their wishes and abilities. As a result, a child who enters school under the pressure of his parents will receive a diploma, not a specialty, after graduation. Naturally, neither he nor the society will benefit from such specialization. In addition to practicing psychologists, the advice of school and family physicians also plays an important role in determining which profession students are eligible for in secondary schools. When advising healthy students on the choice of profession, the pediatrician should take into account that it allows him to develop into a well-rounded person. When choosing a profession for a student with a disability, it is advisable to consult with a doctor. A student with a disability should be directed to a profession that does not lead to the development of a disability in the course of employment. Therefore, the choice of profession requires the cooperation of parents, school teachers and doctors.

It would be expedient for parents to pay more attention to the following in directing their children to the right profession:

- to follow the interests, inclinations and abilities of children from an early age, regardless of their indifference to education;
- Each parent should be in close contact with the class teacher, school psychologist, youth

leader, doctor, to find out what subjects his child is interested in, what science and sports clubs he participates in;

- Parents should fully inform their children about their professions, arouse their interest and provide information about other professions;

- Examine the child's health with a neighborhood and school doctor to see if it is appropriate for the profession in which he or she is interested;

- to choose a professional college only according to the interests of the child and to give him the opportunity to study.

To the school career guidance specialist (school practitioner psychologist) - now it is more difficult to form a positive attitude to each student to choose an independent profession, the need for interest. Before directing students to a profession, it is first necessary to form their perception of the profession.

The professional information that students themselves receive through interactions with various professions (teachers, medical, trade and catering workers, the military, businessmen, farmers, etc.) also influences career choice. Play activities (watching TV, watching videos, computer and sports games, online communication) also give students an idea of their profession.

Therefore, it is important to emphasize the importance of career guidance not only in the educational process in school and in the classroom, but also in the career through extracurricular and out-of-school education.

However, no detailed work has been done in this direction so far. Given the fact that students, especially older school-age students, know their profession, school and extracurricular activities can play an important role in shaping their worldview in this area, it is necessary to study its current state and conduct research on its full potential. It is also important to ensure the continuity of vocational guidance.

In collaboration with mentors, parents and representatives of secondary special vocational education, students should form and develop skills and abilities such as professional decision-making, conscious career choice, professional adaptation and the development of a plan to achieve their goals. After all, the documents on building a society based on a market economy emphasize that teaching students to choose an independent profession (through self-assessment of their capabilities) is a very important and necessary task. Accordingly, it would be more appropriate for psychologists, methodologists, diagnostic center staff and practicing psychologists to work together with the general public to develop career guidance and methods for career choice. Therefore, in order to rationally organize the choice of profession, it is necessary to take into account the needs of specialists in our country and, accordingly, to determine the suitability of schoolchildren for this or that profession, depending on their inclinations, aspirations, interests, opportunities, integrity and physical abilities.

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